

A corpus-based study of L2 learners' semantic prosody awareness

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In this study, I explored L2 learners' semantic prosody awareness and potential developmental patterns by using corpus as evidence. Semantic prosody is the tendency of certain words to occur with positive or negative language (Ellis, Frey, & Jalkanen, 2009). For instance, the verb 'cause' would be more strongly associated with negative connotations rather than positive (e.g. 'cause danger'). Furthermore, semantic prosody is not realized within a single item, often revealed only from the surrounding environment. For L2 learners, however, exposure to these lexical items in context is limited, which may lead to communicatively inadequate utterances (Omidian & Siyanova-Chanturia, 2020). Several studies used controlled elicited experiments to explore L2 learners' semantic prosody awareness, but the findings regarding developmental patterns remain unclear (Dushku & Paek, 2021; McGee, 2012). The current study therefore aims to answer the following research questions.

- 1) Do higher-level L2 learners show higher semantic prosody awareness in writing than lower-level learners?
- 2) How are L2 learners' semantic prosody awareness in writing different from (or similar to) native speakers?

Using learner corpus, this study investigated whether L2 learners' semantic prosody awareness develops as their proficiency level increases. For learner corpus, the written essay portion of the ICNALE corpus that consists of L2 learners' argumentative essays was used. I then divided this corpus into two sub-corpora according to the CEFR levels to explore the possible developmental trajectories. For reference corpus, I used the LOCNESS, which includes British and American university students' argumentative essays. The pre-selected verbs that have been shown to have strong positive or negative semantic associations in previous literature (e.g., guarantee, commit, completely) were first identified. Then, using sentiment analysis, I calculated the value of semantic prosody for each instance and examined and compared the patterns across the three corpora. Findings from this study will contribute to the uncovering of the developmental aspects of semantic prosody awareness.

References

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